

Circle packing inside a regular nonagon: supplemental material

Paolo Amore

Facultad de Ciencias, CUICBAS, Universidad de Colima,
Bernal Díaz del Castillo 340, Colima, Colima, Mexico
paolo@ucol.mx

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Abstract

We report the configurations of $2 \leq N \leq 200$ congruent disks packed inside a regular nonagon obtained using the algorithms of ref. [1].

1 Introduction

We report here the densest configurations for circle packing inside a regular nonagon that we have found using the algorithms described in ref. [1] for $2 \leq N \leq 200$. Although we cannot claim that these configurations correspond to global maxima of the packing fraction, they provide good lower bounds to the packing fraction. Such bounds may be improved in the future, either by performing more intensive numerical calculations or by coming up with more efficient algorithms. The reader should refer to [1] for a description of the algorithms and a discussion of previous work.

This document is organized as follows: in section 2 we display the densest configurations of N congruent disks packed inside a regular nonagon, for $2 \leq N \leq 200$; in section 3 we display the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations previously found. The data corresponding to the configurations reported in this document may be found at the repository [2] or directly from the author.

2 Densest configurations found for $N \leq 200$

The configurations are plotted assigning a color code described in [1], which depends on the number of contacts of each disk. Since the calculation is numerical, this information has to be assessed within a given tolerance: in our case, if the distance between two disks exceeds by 10^{-6} the minimal distance among any two disks in the configuration, they are regarded as being in contact. Refinement is typically a slow process and it could be demanding when N is

large: configurations with a large number of black disks (i.e. disks that are not in contact with any other disk or with the walls of the container) are most likely improvable upon performing a suitable refinement.

Table 1: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular nonagon for $2 \leq N \leq 79$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
2	0.480860690389	0.502271353193	41	0.132473464591	0.781468556224
3	0.450678162524	0.661796013624	42	0.131089702201	0.783892133612
4	0.395232683712	0.678633909137	43	0.129501438595	0.783226735184
5	0.352206160693	0.673649145167	44	0.128171142526	0.785060361565
6	0.321188475783	0.672265805188	45	0.127201761734	0.790803583311
7	0.316435787353	0.761270657441	46	0.125622435834	0.78842813598
8	0.288933606801	0.725363949019	47	0.124425326049	0.790287831695
9	0.264727783683	0.685032883033	48	0.123505835511	0.795217732042
10	0.254814656089	0.705210336498	49	0.121838884231	0.790019422668
11	0.250753377701	0.751200954116	50	0.120964163047	0.794608700994
12	0.24331722824	0.771608191057	51	0.119690243765	0.793519386013
13	0.227702746932	0.732065186086	52	0.118705963533	0.795826288088
14	0.221049182018	0.74297760296	53	0.117386481464	0.793198533081
15	0.211711448132	0.730213414238	54	0.116393603009	0.794551123866
16	0.20740330104	0.747517171647	55	0.115464005331	0.796389983291
17	0.199389671625	0.734047391663	56	0.114541740987	0.79796795101
18	0.196449564621	0.75447440037	57	0.113545657206	0.798152309365
19	0.194579251484	0.781297653383	58	0.112826137539	0.801894615776
20	0.187357378977	0.762502834248	59	0.111651749248	0.798827370639
21	0.18266671175	0.761040867532	60	0.110645001044	0.797782870172
22	0.17692213761	0.747923017462	61	0.109840357754	0.799325328202
23	0.173790392367	0.754482595102	62	0.108999662407	0.800040287724
24	0.17018582654	0.754966846204	63	0.108360069733	0.803431700287
25	0.167429888951	0.76115981031	64	0.107258803299	0.799679072052
26	0.165098269544	0.769711991735	65	0.10676419534	0.804700889242
27	0.163332030349	0.782305435548	66	0.105719738729	0.801172363825
28	0.159363996685	0.772339629104	67	0.104896851789	0.800699529239
29	0.157102553898	0.777381766899	68	0.104289210361	0.803262575116
30	0.154316890493	0.775921961391	69	0.103932773834	0.809513301636
31	0.151669734555	0.774514244254	70	0.102948397539	0.805762560233
32	0.149548357796	0.777290101603	71	0.102337510651	0.807602971242
33	0.147454090018	0.779287030977	72	0.101903338466	0.812043291734
34	0.145733308872	0.784271495055	73	0.100926906839	0.807619225969
35	0.143989066189	0.788128326369	74	0.100220284365	0.807258902692
36	0.142492834502	0.793886495202	75	0.0993549569907	0.804100264435
37	0.140856382056	0.797305288252	76	0.0987320544741	0.80463663632
38	0.13755939828	0.780969356853	77	0.098262598593	0.807489860006
39	0.136132915409	0.784983919119	78	0.0978737631177	0.811515909121
40	0.134180360633	0.782181901937	79	0.097489041209	0.81547110576

Table 2: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular nonagon for $80 \leq N \leq 161$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
80	0.0966646990581	0.811887127268	121	0.0790691126479	0.821616140679
81	0.0961548162174	0.813386509888	122	0.0787070487784	0.820837047151
82	0.0954449106328	0.811314552302	123	0.0782510453354	0.818003702438
83	0.0947909798244	0.809994331206	124	0.077945933565	0.818235792844
84	0.0941874876829	0.809348514539	125	0.0775968148628	0.817462172688
85	0.0936282002821	0.809286207429	126	0.077387218987	0.819556477694
86	0.0930429046891	0.808602041717	127	0.0770993044241	0.819925707031
87	0.0925751399717	0.809800181028	128	0.0769765648575	0.82375276376
88	0.0920857043162	0.810470035038	129	0.076590281695	0.821877149763
89	0.0914667385305	0.808697789254	130	0.0763169035378	0.822346212794
90	0.0909521673961	0.808608825659	131	0.0759665115491	0.82108009739
91	0.0903533224457	0.806862456971	132	0.0757145831253	0.821869501063
92	0.0899722983786	0.808863650687	133	0.0754494368167	0.822306092359
93	0.0897060000005	0.812822645078	134	0.075104152235	0.820923252189
94	0.0892555897914	0.813333319026	135	0.074950992007	0.823679773067
95	0.0888932478307	0.815325481222	136	0.0746274507429	0.822632727602
96	0.0885276232658	0.817144204039	137	0.0745206421962	0.826311138585
97	0.0878192984026	0.812496544733	138	0.0742862924572	0.827115798194
98	0.0873529842483	0.812178391598	139	0.0737809979149	0.821814334669
99	0.0868382887054	0.810825819145	140	0.0736934136904	0.825762672644
100	0.0864129823787	0.811013065212	141	0.0733470636886	0.823861938791
101	0.0860505948387	0.812267336775	142	0.0730069845933	0.822028791333
102	0.085611522387	0.811959698906	143	0.0727861583705	0.822817454336
103	0.085255598892	0.813116746996	144	0.0723860162742	0.819486316945
104	0.0848050285077	0.812356033553	145	0.0722131665919	0.821241038268
105	0.084451789407	0.8133488807	146	0.0719767441823	0.821499140635
106	0.0841258707881	0.814769705284	147	0.0718309714804	0.823778925102
107	0.0836760517784	0.813684418881	148	0.0714347590162	0.820258511398
108	0.0833981260344	0.815842267833	149	0.0713207695735	0.82316741764
109	0.0829221845547	0.814025162965	150	0.0711909336368	0.825677591714
110	0.0825930933806	0.814985743371	151	0.0709308092506	0.825119097343
111	0.0823074637903	0.816716406933	152	0.0707063781297	0.825335703945
112	0.0820839046821	0.819603679822	153	0.0705659700902	0.827469367802
113	0.0818892774685	0.823004830251	154	0.070413306489	0.829277839534
114	0.0817639834054	0.827749250768	155	0.0702578429759	0.830981173516
115	0.0816333081878	0.832343314901	156	0.0700508230418	0.831420914533
116	0.0809164077954	0.824899499864	157	0.0697079648288	0.8285797618
117	0.0804968831344	0.823405670023	158	0.0694600495061	0.827936684979
118	0.0801980621291	0.824289215983	159	0.0691826509091	0.826535258794
119	0.0796859450387	0.820692148606	160	0.0687678200423	0.821789067556
120	0.079357872111	0.820788261244	161	0.0686067481699	0.823056043824

Table 3: radii and density of the best packing configurations inside a regular nonagon for $162 \leq N \leq 200$.

N	r	ρ	N	r	ρ
162	0.0682893183687	0.820522382425	182	0.0648478647125	0.831251823228
163	0.0682839026868	0.825456394249	183	0.0647478824927	0.833243801512
164	0.0679558990174	0.822560849117	184	0.0644907940837	0.831157128819
165	0.067995483022	0.828540863962	185	0.0643585609729	0.832250836614
166	0.0678778877303	0.830681595878	186	0.0641364683791	0.83098443803
167	0.0675864685794	0.82852543088	187	0.063939590342	0.830330837842
168	0.0672938069052	0.826283992276	188	0.0635903775281	0.825677629349
169	0.0673485374287	0.832554944546	189	0.063521229556	0.828265283252
170	0.0670081641056	0.829037588893	190	0.0634712480642	0.831337822094
171	0.0667802505348	0.828251174922	191	0.063304994817	0.831340971327
172	0.0667688123384	0.832809386673	192	0.0630549107414	0.829103830048
173	0.0663584201163	0.827385757205	193	0.0630859707431	0.834243346419
174	0.0661951542202	0.828078496551	194	0.0628417192086	0.832085028267
175	0.0659896429719	0.827674296217	195	0.0627165624357	0.833045966373
176	0.0658138621394	0.827975115243	196	0.0626909209277	0.836633466241
177	0.0657543666986	0.831174722559	197	0.0624415320563	0.834224977581
178	0.0654994545624	0.829402292497	198	0.0623316818621	0.83551209886
179	0.0654960592357	0.833975386848	199	0.0622111041817	0.836486156454
180	0.0654810701661	0.838250660558	200	0.0619476938916	0.833585487659
181	0.0651146132134	0.833499545494			

Figure 1: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 2: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 3: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 4: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 5: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 6: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 7: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 8: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 9: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 10: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 11: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 12: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 13: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 14: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 15: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 16: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 17: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

3 Voronoi diagrams

We report the Voronoi diagrams for the configurations of section 2. We use the same color scheme as before, where the colors of each cell depends on the number of sides. One can assign a topological charge to the cell, depending on the number of sides of the cell and on the location of the cell: for internal cells, the topological charge is $q_{int} = 6 - \ell$, where ℓ is the number of sides, while for cells on the border $q_{border} = 5 - \ell$. Vertices from which emanate more than three lines carry a topological charge $q_{vert} = -2(n - 3)$, where n is the number of lines.

The Euler theorem of topology requires that the sum of all topological charges be equal to 6, regardless of the complexity of the configuration, but it does not forbid changing a number of cells with the same number of cells with different individual topological charges as long as the total charge is kept the same. For example, one could substitute two hexagonal internal cells with a pair consisting of pentagonal and heptagonal cells. See [1] for a more detailed discussion.

Figure 18: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($2 \leq N \leq 13$).

Figure 19: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($14 \leq N \leq 25$).

Figure 20: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($26 \leq N \leq 37$).

Figure 21: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($38 \leq N \leq 49$).

Figure 22: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($50 \leq N \leq 61$).

Figure 23: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($62 \leq N \leq 73$).

Figure 24: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($74 \leq N \leq 85$).

Figure 25: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($86 \leq N \leq 97$).

Figure 26: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($98 \leq N \leq 109$).

Figure 27: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($110 \leq N \leq 121$).

Figure 28: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($122 \leq N \leq 133$).

Figure 29: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($134 \leq N \leq 145$).

Figure 30: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($146 \leq N \leq 157$).

Figure 31: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($158 \leq N \leq 169$).

Figure 32: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($170 \leq N \leq 181$).

Figure 33: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($182 \leq N \leq 193$).

Figure 34: Best packing for N equal circles inside a regular nonagon ($194 \leq N \leq 200$).

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References

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- [2] Paolo Amore, "Coordinates of the packing configurations of arXiv:2212.12287 ", <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7574070>